

Effects of Climate Change in Heritage of Buildings, Sculpture and Painting at Himalayan Region

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ABSTRACT

Environmental condition change is a real threat that the humanity is facing at the moment. As the vulnerability of hill ecosystems to the changes in the climate is well established, more or less the changes in the climate that they feel have aggravated their hardships by making them more and more vulnerable to its effects. The substance of human life is qualitatively and quantitatively affected by climate change issues like rise in sea level, increase in surface air temperature, irregular monsoon, severe storm frequency, changes in precipitation and humidity etc. Environmental status change is studied in universal, followed by its impacts on heritage buildings, sculpture and painting of coastal regions in North India. In recent period the modification about natural environment and climate determined in Uttarakhand state negatively affected the monumental buildings, the cultural riches of the state that they have been worn out by several natural effects long period. However, since monumental buildings have outstanding importance due to their identity of transferring ancient era information to the future generations, abrasive effects of rain water, salt and some chemicals involved in water, molecule carried by wind and air pollution. Numerous World Heritage situation are living places which depend on their communities to be sustained and maintained.

Environmental condition modification has consequences for the entire of human being and the outcome of human creativity. In the case of cultural World Heritage sites these consequences will be evident in at least two primary ways direct physical effects on the site, building or structure and the effects on social structures and surroundings that could lead to alteration in, or even the migration of, societies that are presently uphold World Heritage position. The implications of the latter are not well appreciated, even if the nature of the impacts will vary depending on the nature of the International Heritage place. The character of social heritage is closely related to the environmental condition. The rural scenery has improved in consequence to the plant species that are able to flourish in various climatic regimes. The urban landscape and the built heritage have been designed with the topical climate in mind. The stability of cultural heritage is, therefore, closely tied to its physical phenomenon with the land and the region. Where World Heritage sites are in use by local communities there may be force for important accommodative changes to accept use and occupation to continue. one needs to specify indicators to assess the overall impact of climate on Cultural Global Heritage. Climate change can be subtle and can occur over a long period of time. However, some Climate Change parameters such a freezing, temperature and relative humidity shock can change by large amounts over a short time period. To identify the greatest world Climate Change risks and impacts on cultural heritage buildings, sculpture, painting, Old Traditional good Design of Textile, Design Wood work.

INTRODUCTION:

Uttarakhand is famous as 'Dev Bhoomi', at about every hill top there is a place of worship. After leaving the doors of Devbhoomi, Haridwar, the beauty of the creation is visible all over. One can see it in the simple nature of the people, beautiful valleys, fountains, rivers, mountains, flowers. Open eyes and you will realize a beauty. We have tried to collect several information from various point; on different temples and spiritual places across Uttarakhand. Different Gods and Goddesses in three dimensional forms and are meant

exclusively for worshipping purposes. These idols are braced out of fine clay mixed with color. They are activated through various color to make them looking more attractive. During the celebration of Kartik Sankranti, Lord Shiva's images are made which are famous as Dekaras, and these depict the marriage of Shiva with Parvathi, the daughter of Himalaya. Uttarakhand provides most suitable environmental condition for animals like sheep, angora rabbits and pashmina goats. Wool extracted from animals like sheep is

utilized to make products like kaaleen, pankhi, thulma (thick blanket) chutka etc. The designs and techniques used are influenced by the near Tibet. While Johar-Munisiyari in Pithoragarh district is famous for producing woolen carpets and thulma. Almora has been producing its famous tweeds, woolen carpets and artistic woolen shawls. The other places where this craft has been skillful are Bageshwar, Nainital, Dehradun, Chamoli, Rudraprayag and Uttarkashi. Heritage Building can be represented as the sum of the social, economic, political and cultural developments. Environmental condition can be defined as the whole atmospheric events such as rainfall, temperature, wind, pressure and humidity that cause certain damages on the important buildings for long time.

ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION OF UTTARAKHAND

Uttarakhand has a gross area of 53,483 km², of which 86% is mountainous and 65% is covered by forest. Most of the northern part of the state is covered by high Himalayan peaks and glaciers. In the first half of the nineteenth century, the expanding development of Indian roads, railways and other physical infrastructure was giving rise to concerns over indiscriminate logging, particularly in the Himalaya. Two of the most important rivers in Hinduism originate in the glaciers of Uttarakhand, the Ganges at Gangotri and the Yamuna at Yamunotri. They are fed by myriad lakes, glacial melts and streams. These two along with Badrinath and Kedarnath form the Chota Char Dham, a holy pilgrimage for the Hindus.

Summers: Summers, in most of the Uttarakhand are mostly pleasant, but some places do have hot climate. The temperatures, in places like Haridwar, Rishikesh, etc. can reach the 40 degrees Celsius mark. Coupled with humidity, this can be pretty uncomfortable. The summer season of Uttarakhand extends from April to June.

Winters: Winters in Uttarakhand are very cold, with many places receiving regular snowfalls. Temperature during the winter season ranges from sub zero to about 15 degrees Celsius. The winter season in Uttarakhand generally extends from October to February.

Monsoon: During the period of July to September, lies the monsoon season of Uttarakhand. The temperature ranges from 15 to 25 degrees Celsius at most of the places, during this time. . The state receives approximately 90% of its annual rainfall in this season. It is also one of the most pleasant seasons of Uttarakhand.

Figure1: Map Uttarakhand, Source: <https://www.bragitoff.com>

**HERITAGE BUILDINGS, SCULPTURE, PAINTINGS
EFFECTS OF CLIMATE**

Figure2: Baleshwar Temple,

Figure3: Champawat, Baleshwar,

Figure4: Hrishikesh, Lord Vishnu

Figure5: Sculpture at Baleshwar

Figure 6: Bells-dome, Baleshwar

Figure 10: Idols in Baijnath Temple

Figure 7: Tungnath is, Panch Kedar

Figure 11: Stone carving work, Champawat, Baleshwar

Figure 8: Main Temple in Jageshwar

Figure 12: Badrinath Temple

Figure 9: Jageshwar Temples, Almora Hills

Figure 13: Badrinath

Figure 14: Kedarnath or Lord Shiva

Figure 18: Garhwali Nath, Courtesy: Vibhor Yadav.

Figure 15: Kedarnath

Figure 19: The Miniature Paintings in Guru Ram Rai Darbar Src

Painting

Figure 16: 'Garhwal Painting', by Jwala Ram

Figure 17: 'Panch patthar' Courtesy: Vibhor Yadav.

CONCLUSION

Uttarakhand is also affluent in cultural heritage, which has been kept lively through with Arts and Crafts of Uttarakhand. The Handicrafts of Uttarakhand has the actual for great value . Uttarakhand is famous for its temple architecture, wood carvings, paintings and traditional ornaments. Uttarakhand had traditional artisans including "Tamtas" (Copper Smith) well-known for their hand-made implement, and other artisans making useful household items from Bamboo and other commercial wood Crafts of Uttarakhand. At that place are many Heritage Temple such as Kedarnath Temple- Gahrwal, Badrinath Temple, Chitai Golu Temple- Almora, Devidhura Bagwal Temple- Champawat, Purnagiri Temple- Champawat, Kainchi Dham Temple- Bhowali- Almora Road, Patal Bhuvneshwar Cave- Pithoragarh, Jageshwar Dham Temple- Almora, Binsar Mahadev Temple- Ranikhet, Chandrabadni Temple- Tehri, Kandoliya Temple- Pauri, Jwalpa Devi Temple- Pauri, Koteswar Mahadev Temple- Rudraprayag, Kartik Swami Temple- Rudraprayag, Hariyali Devi Temple- Rudraprayag, Kamleshwar Temple- Srinagar Garhwal, Umra Narayan Temple- Rudraprayag, Kalimath Temple- Rudraprayag etc. located in different regions of Uttarakhand. They have been constructed using stone, natural construction materials that present serious devolve are observed on them. These devolve have occurred not only because of the age of the structures but also mostly due to the climate and factors. Environmental condition can be defined as the entire atmospheric events such as rainfall, temperature, wind, pressure and humidity that cause certain damages on the Heritage buildings, Temple in the time period. Three different seasons in Uttarakhand cause some problems against Heritage Temple. The deteriorate related to climate conditions on the Heritage buildings, in Uttarakhand present regional differences and happen due to temperature variation between seasons and day night.

The capillary motion of water within the composition of the Heritage construction. The atmospheric condition effects of rain water, salts and several chemicals existing in water, particles carried by winds and air pollution, in which such damage under the influence of the sun and air that have been noted.

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1. www.uttarakhand.ws (Source:Figure-2,Figure-3,Figure-5,Figure-6,Figure-7,Figure-8,Figure-10,Figure-11,Figure-12)
2. www.therishikesh.com (Source:Figure 4: Hrishikesh, Lord Vishnu)
3. www.clicksandtales.com, (Source:Figure 9: Jageshwar Temples, Almora Hills)
4. www.godzhere.blogspot.com/2015/08 (Source: Figure 13: Badrinath)
5. www.news18.com/news/india/ (Source: Figure 14: Kedarnath or Lord Shiva)
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7. www.srinagargarhwal.com/srinagar-molaram-story.php, (Source: Figure 16)
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